

My New Idea for Optimized Combinatorial Techniques

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Abstract: The optimized binomial coefficient or binomial expansion has been derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. This binomial coefficient is a methodological advance in the areas of combinatorics and theoretical computer science. This paper presents a new theorem with binomial coefficient for researchers working in the theory of computation.

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My new Idea

When I was trying to make the multiple summations of geometric series [1-7], a new idea was generated in my mind to build the sum of multiple geometric series or multiple summations of geometric series along with optimized binomial coefficient.

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \text{ is the multiple summations of geometric series [8,9]}$$

and I named the optimized binomial coefficient for the following binomial expansion [9-15]:

$$V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)(r+3)\cdots(r+n-1)(r+n)}{n!}, \quad (n \geq 1, r \geq 0 \text{ \& } n, r \in N),$$

where $N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots\}$, is the set of natural number including zero element and $n!$ is the factorial of nonnegative integer n . For example, $3! = 1 \times 2 \times 3 = 6$ and $0! = 1$.

My next development, after the multiple summations of geometrics and the optimized binomial coefficient, was the following binomial series [7]:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r+1} x^i = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i + \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^r x^i + \sum_{i=2}^n V_{i-2}^r x^i + \cdots + \sum_{i=n-1}^n V_{i-(n-1)}^r x^i + \sum_{i=n}^n V_{i-n}^r x^i.$$

After this development, I generated the following binomial identities one after another.

- (1) $V_0^n = 1 \quad (n \geq 1 \in N)$; (2) $V_r^n = V_n^r \quad (n, r \geq 1 \text{ \& } n, r \in N)$; (3) $V_r^{n+1} - V_r^n = V_{r-1}^n$;
 (4) $1 + V_1^1 + V_1^2 + V_1^3 \cdots \cdots V_1^n = V_2^n$; (5) $V_0^n + V_1^n + V_2^n + V_3^n \cdots + V_{r-1}^n + V_r^n = V_r^{n+1}$;
 (6) $\sum_{i=0}^n (i+1)V_i^{n-i} = (n+2)2^{n-1}$; (7) $\sum_{i=0}^n (i-1)V_i^{n-i} = (n-2)2^{n-1}$;

$$(8) \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n; \quad (9) \sum_{i=0}^n i \times V_i^{n-i} = n2^{n-1}; \quad (10) V_n^n = 2V_{n-1}^n;$$

$$(11) V_1^1 + V_2^2 + V_3^3 + V_n^n = 2(V_0^1 + V_1^2 + V_2^3 + \dots + V_{n-1}^n) \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n V_i^i = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^i;$$

$$(12) \sum_{i=1}^r V_i^{n+1} = \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^0 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^1 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^2 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^3 + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{n-1} + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^n;$$

$$(13) \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{n+1} x^i = \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^n x^i + \sum_{i=1}^r V_{i-1}^n x^i + \sum_{i=2}^r V_{i-2}^n x^i + \dots + \sum_{i=r-1}^r V_{i-(r-1)}^n x^i + \sum_{i=r}^r V_{i-r}^n x^i.$$

For other theorems and factorial and binomial expansions refer to my previous papers online and references of this article.

Now, I present the following new theorem (binomial identity) for researchers and students in the world.

Theorem : $k \times V_n^n + (l \times V_n^{n-1}) = 3 \times k \times l \times V_n^{n-1}$, where $k, l \geq 1$ & $k, l \in N$.

Before proving the theorem, we have to understand the relationship between optimized and traditional binomial coefficients [11-15].

The traditional binomial coefficient is $nC_r = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}$.

$V_x^y = V_y^x$ is the optimized combination. Let $z = x + y$. Then, $zC_x = zC_y$, ($x, y, z \in N$).

For example,

$$V_3^5 = V_5^3 = (5+3)C_3 = (5+3)C_5 = 56.$$

Also, $V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = \frac{n!}{n!0!} = 1$ and $V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1$ ($\because 0! = 1$).

Proof of the theorem. we know that the binomial identity(10) $\Rightarrow V_n^n = 2V_{n-1}^n = 2V_n^{n-1}$. By substituting this identity (10) in the left hand side of new theorem (binomial identity), we get $k \times V_n^n + (l \times V_n^{n-1}) = k \times 2V_n^{n-1} + (l \times V_n^{n-1}) = (2k+l)V_n^{n-1}$, where $k, l \geq 1$ & $k, l \in N$.

For example, let $k = l = 1$ and $n = 2$. $V_2^2 + V_2^1 = 3V_2^1 \Rightarrow 9 = 9$.

Hence, theorem is proved.

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